

AI in BI - A Conceptual Framework

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Abstract: Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a rapidly evolving field with numerous applications, some of which are in the domain of Business Intelligence (BI). While BI has got a good conceptual framework, the applications of AI in BI are quite fragmented and the pace of development is rapid. The AI and BI product organizations tend to focus on the benefits of their respective products. But, a conceptual framework for AI in BI which includes them in a meaningful way is still lacking. This paper aims to provide the same, along with examples from the Business Domains.

Keywords: Business Intelligence; Artificial Intelligence; Framework; RDBMS; Data warehouse

I. A BRIEF HISTORY OF BUSINESS INTELLIGENCE (BI)

BI has gained considerable popularity over the past decade. Although the term was first introduced in 1965 and picked up momentum in the mid-late 1980s, it was only in the early 1990s that the phrase entered public discourse.

The emergence of Relational Database Management Systems (RDBMS) was a significant step forward in the 70s. Edgar Codd, in his paper, “A Relational Model of Data for Large Shared Data Banks” [1], completely transformed the way databases were conceived from “a simple means of organization” to, “a tool for querying data to find relations hidden within.” In the late 1980s and early 1990s the RDBMSs really took off. The term “data warehouse” emerged in the 70s and would ultimately change the way business intelligence would operate, says Furhaad Shah [2]

In the 1980s, “business data warehouse” was developed by IBM. It was intended to provide an architectural model for the flow of data from operational systems to decision support environments.

Data that had previously been spread across numerous sources like Online Transaction Processing (OLTP), historical repository of data and external sources could now be held together in one place with data warehousing. This allowed business users to search the information efficiently and to gather an overarching strategic picture of their model and functions. [3]

Over the years, Extract, transform, and load (ETL) utilities were developed to move data from disparate data sources, transform them into the common data warehouse format and then load them to a common data warehouse. [3]

These warehouses were specifically designed to support the analytical functions required for business intelligence (OLAP, or online analytical processing), making it possible for users to execute rapid and complex analytical queries.

The BI landscape has grown from a competition between a handful of competitors to a booming and highly successful market.

II. BI FRAMEWORK – FROM DATA TO DECISIONS

BI can be termed as a journey from Data to Decisions. The Data Warehousing Institute (TDWI) had formalized a BI framework which describes this journey in precise terms. Given below is the framework (Fig. 1) [4]

Fig 1. Business Intelligence Framework

The flow of business is shown on the left side of the framework. It starts with Business Drivers which cause a need for action. These could be external (market conditions, political/economical environment etc.) or internal (vision of the top management etc.). The Business Goals are set based on the drivers. These are the desired outcome of action. Business strategies (plans) are arrived at and Business Tactics (implementation of strategies) formulated. The operations yield the result.

Let us take an example from the airlines domain to illustrate the flow of business. An airlines is facing revenue loss (business driver) and wants to improve the situation. They set a target for their revenue growth in the next 6 months (business goal). They want to cut down the routes which are making losses and increase more flights in routes which are earning profits (business strategy). They get in to action and make the route changes, communicate the same to the public, make appropriate changes to their schedules, update their web portal, inform their agents and